

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES ON THE ZARAFSHAN RIVER AND THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF THE RIVER

Utayeva R.O., Ro`ziqulova F.B., Pardayev F.F.

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, graduate students

Abstract. The article describes the changes in the water composition of the Zarafshan basin as a result of anthropogenic influence. At the same time, the sphere of influence of the enterprises located on the banks of the river has been revealed.

Key words: population economy, anthropogenic impact, ecology, water resources, river.

The Zarafshan Valley is considered one of the oldest and most important agricultural regions of Central Asia, and the large cities of Samarkand and Bukhara are located in the basin. The river, which has its own significance in our republic, starts from the Zarafshan glacier and is fed by snow and ice. In the mountainous area, it joins more than 70 tributaries, and flows over 300 km in the mountainous area, and after passing into the territory of Uzbekistan, it begins to flow from the plain.

Zarafshan River is a source for the economy of Samarkand, Navoi and Bukhara regions. After the Zarafshan river reaches the plain, it mainly feeds the irrigated fields in the Middle and Lower Zarafshan regions. The average long-term water consumption of the river at the Ravothoja dam is 276 dm³/sec., the minimum water consumption is 43.3 m³/sec., and the maximum water consumption is 429.0 m³/sec. It is known that the quantitative assessment of water resources, the study of hydrological issues related to their effective use and finding their specific solutions are of great practical importance. Because of this, the study of the annual changes and distribution of river flow is considered one of the most urgent issues today.

With the development of science and technology, the river water was released to neighboring areas through modern irrigation facilities and was used for new settlements and industrial enterprises. Later, along with the effective use of river water, the problem of its protection arose.

The Zarafshan River has reached the Samarkand and Bukhara-Karakul oases, and now the composition of the water has completely changed. The seepage water, waste water from industrial enterprises and agriculture have changed its composition. The water of the Zarafshan river is currently used only for agriculture. Mainly, as a result of industrial enterprises launched in the cities of Samarkand, Kattakorgan, and Navoi, they throw their waste water into the river after half-cleaning - without cleaning, as a result of applying a lot of toxic chemical fertilizers to the cotton fields, the river water is polluted and the population is deprived of drinking water. there is a problem of supply.

If we start monitoring the level of cleanliness of the river from the eastern part of Samarkand region, as a result of the water flowing from the livestock farms of Jomboy district, it is affecting the drinking water of the city of Samarkand. Also, the pig farm of the state farm named Ulugbek, the Samarkand meat processing plant, the enterprises of "Obvodstroyindustriya" and the area from the city of Samarkand to the city of Kattakorgan dumped a lot of household waste along the river. excluded. This has a great impact on water pollution. At the same time, the Kattakorgan city-food trade subsidiary farm; As a result of continuous dumping of meat processing plant and farms of Khatirchi district and other wastes into clean water, the water content of the Middle Zarafshan basin is polluted, and as a result of the addition of ditch water, an excess of salt, along with other substances, was found. This causes the destruction of flora and fauna of the basin. Under the influence of these factors, the amount of nitrogen compounds, heavy metal ions, phenols, oil products in Zarafshan water is 5-6 times higher than normal, the hardness and salinity of water is 2 times higher, and the level of pollution is 24 times higher.

Shavdar, Siyob, Chashma, Obirakhmat, Khojaariq, Damarik tributaries of the Zarafshan River pass through the city of Samarkand. The location of the urban waterways in the infrastructure has changed its structure, the waterways have been covered with pavements and turned into waste collection routes. The Samarkand Mining Plant, located on the banks of the Obimashkhad stream, receives 3600 m³ of water from the stream per day, and 3000 m³ of it is polluted. In this way, hydrogen sulfide and ammonia compounds are being saturated. In addition, there are car wash stations on the banks of these ditches. At a time when river waters are becoming more and more polluted, underground waters are increasingly being used in various sectors of the national economy.

Groundwater is widely used to provide water to pastures, settlements, industries and several other production-related processes. The water of many artesian wells flows from the mouth of the existing pipes non-stop, day and night. The surroundings of the wells have turned into lakes and swamps.

It is said that the continuous flow of water from the wells will cause the amount of water under the ground to expand more and more, the pressure of the well will decrease, and in short, it will lead to large-scale negative consequences. In recent years, it has become clear that as a result of the indiscriminate use of salt, brackish water, toxic chemicals, and chemical fertilizers, the composition of running water and groundwater is deteriorating. Nitrates in these waters have increased more than ever. The current situation is causing several major problems in the use of water resources.

Due to the development of agriculture in the Zarafshan oasis, agricultural crops are irrigated at least 3-4 times during the vegetation period. Most of the waste water produced as a result of irrigation of irrigated lands is added to the Zarafshan river or canals. As a result of the addition of wastewater from field irrigation to the river, the concentration of nitrate compounds in the river water is increasing year by year and has increased by more than 10 times the current maximum amount.

In the pollution of all water bodies in the oasis, the influence of anthropogenic factors that occur as a result of human economic activity plays a major role. In almost all large settlements located along the Zarafshon River, there are no special garbage dumps, or the accumulation of various wastes in the existing garbage dumps, due to the fact that the removal of garbage is not controlled and neutralized in time, a large part of the waste enters the river beds, even directly into the river water. is pouring out.

Disobedience to the maintenance of the sanitary zone on both banks of the river, the absence of liquid waste treatment facilities in the centers of the districts, leads to the contamination of water sources with various toxic chemicals. Nitrate, chromium, copper oxides in the river water are 2-3 times more than the specified amounts. It should be noted that the Zarafshan River and large canals that have been receiving water since ancient times supply the population of Samarkand, Navoi, Bukhara regions with the main drinking water.

As a result of the emergence of new settlements in the areas irrigated by canal water and irrigation farming of the lands close to the existing settlements, the level of underground water in the villages in the areas with low relief has risen, and the elevations have been underground. and due to the fact that the water flowing from the above-ground parts towards the slope is polluting the walls of the buildings in the villages, the inhabitants are building new settlements in irregular and unplanned areas, which are free from the influence of irrigation water. Newly built settlements require the creation of new roads, power lines and other infrastructure. In addition, the fact that residential buildings are built in the protection zone of the canal in most cases has a great negative impact on ensuring the safety of the population. As a result of the emergence of new settlements along the canal, there are cases of digging small tributaries from the canal or using illegal water through pumps to irrigate private plots of the population, causing certain problems in water use. In conclusion, taking into account the existing shortcomings and problems, water management, ecology

and other competent organizations in the state system should take all legal measures to prevent the existing shortcomings.

References

1. Rakhmatullayev A.R., Khushnazarov I., Abjalilova U. - Changes in the quantity and quality of Zarafshan river water due to human influence / Scientific development and geography. Proceedings of the Republican scientific-practical conference. - Samarkand, 2007.-B. 74-5 28.
2. Hikmatov F.H., Yunusov G`.Kh., Rakhmonov K.R. Hydrological prediction. - Tashkent - 2013. - 141 p. 29.
3. Hikmatov F.H., Haydarov S.A. The formation of air temperature on the formation of the Zarafshan river flow // News of UzMU, No. 3. - Tashkent, 2012. -B. 75-82. 30
4. Rasulov A.R., Hikmatov F.H. General hydrology. - Tashkent: University, 1995.- 175 p.
5. Rasulov A.R., Hikmatov F.H., Aytbayev D.P.. Basics of hydrology. -Tashkent: University 2003. -327 p.